

Piloting a Buddy Program for New Hires

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ABSTRACT

In 2021, the Strauss Health Sciences Library launched a pilot project to enhance the virtual onboarding of new hires. The Covid-19 pandemic required the library to pivot to online interviewing, hiring, and onboarding, with new hires unable to have face-to-face meetings or experience the physical campus. The Buddy Project paired a new hire with a library staff member to provide guidance, support, and advice during the first few months of employment. The program, in tandem with onboarding activities carried out by the supervisor and human resources, provided the new hire with a casual venue to learn about library and campus culture, how the units within the library work to provide information services for the campus, and the goals of various stakeholders in the educational system.

INTRODUCTION

Onboarding is important because it acclimates new hires to their role, the organization's philosophies, and organizational offerings. It also engages new hires and existing employees, creating employees that are committed to the organization's success and helps retain new hires by making them feel like a member of the team. However, based on several recent surveys, onboarding can fall short (Sibisi, 2022). Some companies lacked a structured onboarding process or had a minimal process, which might contribute to the 30% of new hires leaving after six months (CareerBuilder, 2017). Onboarding is a time and money investment: it can take up to one year for an employee to reach their full potential (Zucker, 2021) at an average cost of \$4,100 over salary and benefits (Olmstead, 2022). While training a new hire costs money, replacing one costs even more. According to the Society for Human Resource Management, the average replacement cost of a salaried employee is six to nine months of their salary (McFeely, 2019). There are numerous professional relationships a new hire will have during the onboarding process and beyond. A supervisor directs work schedules, daily activities, and performance expectations. A mentor helps new hires with role-related advice and longer-term career development. A buddy is an informal relationship, assisting new employees for short periods of time and requires little to no specialized training.

PILOT SETTING

The Strauss Health Sciences Library is located on the University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus, the largest academic health center in the Rocky Mountain region. The library serves the clinical, research, educational and community outreach missions of six health professional schools, over 60 centers and institutes, and two nationally ranked partner hospitals. Library staff support the campus's 42 fields of study and degree programs for 4,500 degree-seeking students and 1,100 faculty. When fully staffed, the library has 35 employees. Figure 1 illustrates the library's turnover rate over a five-year period. From 2017 to 2021, the library averaged around

five vacancies, or 14% overall staffing loss a year. Staff departures fell into three main categories: retirement, family-related reasons, or pursuing other positions.

Figure 1: Strauss Health Sciences Library turnover rate from 2017-2019

METHODOLOGY

The Covid-19 pandemic required the library to think about how to improve the onboarding experience for new hires. Traditionally, the hiring process and the onboarding of new hires was conducted in person. The shift to an online environment meant that new hires would miss out on experiencing the physical environment of the library and the campus, and the interpersonal connections made within their unit, or casually around the building or campus. The pilot was meant to supplement, not replace, formal training and onboarding requirements and activities that would be completed by the new hire's supervisor or human resources. To enhance the new hire's experience during their first 4 months of employment, the buddy served as an additional resource to the new hire's supervisor for onboarding. The aim was to ease the transition for the new hire with another library staff member (non-supervisor), and to provide a way for new hires to ask questions that they might be uncomfortable asking their supervisor. We anticipated that the program would fill the gap of serendipitous interactions missed due to remote working.

Guidelines for the Buddy Pilot Program were drafted, and a proposal was reviewed and approved by library leadership. The pilot was launched in 2021, and to date there have been five buddy/new hire pairings, three of which were concluded at the time of publication. When a new hire was made, the position's supervisor put out a call for volunteers and selected a buddy based on the responses received. In some cases, there might have been a compelling reason to request a specific employee based on common interests, work experience or the potential for collaboration between the individuals. It was not a requirement that the buddy be a peer. Once a pairing was made, both parties received the approved guidelines for the pilot.

The buddy worked with the new hire to schedule meetings for a four-month period. The new hire's questions would drive the conversations, or the buddy could address topics like library committees and working groups, how to get around campus, and library culture. The relationship

was meant to be informal, and there was no requirement for reporting back to the supervisor about any of the content of meetings or other forms of correspondence. Participants could opt to continue to meet after the end of the four months.

RESULTS

Qualtrics, a web-based survey tool, was used to develop and distribute a three-question survey to the three pairings that had concluded their four months of meeting. We had an 83% response rate (5 out of 6). We first asked what the new hires and buddies liked about their participation in the pilot. Overall, participants thought the program was beneficial, providing a safe space to ask a variety of questions that the new hire might not feel comfortable asking the supervisor. We then asked what changes they would like to see in the program. Main themes included scheduling in-person over virtual meetings, ensuring privacy of conversations and/or communications unless buddy gave permission to share, and addressing how to transition the program to a peer-to-peer relationship when there is not enough staff that is a "peer" (though the pilot was not designed as a peer-to-peer program). Lastly, we asked participants what they thought the value of the program was to the library. Main themes included feeling more connected and having a better understanding of how the different units within the library work toward a common goal.

DISCUSSION

After three years of operating virtually we hope to begin transitioning back to in-person interviewing and hiring, but continue to offer the Buddy Program. We will need to find effective and efficient ways to improve the program as it moves out of the pilot phase, and find a good metric to determine if the program improves retention rates. We have also discussed expanding the program to all staff, regardless of their hiring date, and we will continue to solicit feedback from current and future participants, and find proactive ways to improve and expand the program.

ENDNOTES

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